

THE CHALLENGES OF YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN POLITICS AND GOVERNANCE; THE ASSESSMENT OF "THE NOT TOO YOUNG TO RUN LAW"

Abstract

Promoting youth representation in politics is a growing global priority. To promote youth leadership and more inclusive politics, youth organizations in Nigeria mobilized successfully for a constitutional reform to lower the eligibility age to run for political office (Not too Young to Run law). The research work focuses on the challenges of youth participation in politics and governance; the assessment of "the not too young to run law". The research applied both primary and secondary data to analyse the problems and also the use of Key Informant Interview (KII). In this research work, we assess challenges of youth participation in politics and governance and whether the Signing of Not too young to Run law as lead to higher level of youth participation in 2023 general elections. We find out that there was a little increase in the percentage of youth aspirants in 2023 general elections and the percentage of youths occupying elective and appointed offices in comparism with 2015 general elections. The research work recommended that there should be a strong agent of socialization, the youths should form coalition of political parties, there should be certain percentage of Youth candidates required from any political party and Government should provide an enabling environment for the youths to participate in Nigeria politics.

1.1 Background of the Study

The concept of politics constitutes those activities which relates to the governance of a nation. It entails making decisions which affects the people of the society (Adebayo, 2018). It also means attaining a position and exercising the power of governance over a given society or nation. It is viewed as the administration of a constitutional system of government. Governance involves exercising control over a territory or state (Asika, 2006). Consequently, Participation is considered as essential. Many institutions and government have demonstrated the need for youth participation in the political process of the nation so as to enhance youth active citizenship, inclusion, integration and effective contribution to the development of democracy and institution of governance. It is believed that this is essential to build a prosperous and developed nation. But, the changing political, cultural and economic realities and developed nation. But, the changing political, cultural and economic realities have greatly affected the active participation of youths in politics and governance (Adisa, 2008).

Many youths are disengaging from democratic and civic activities and concentrating more on professional careers. According to reports, 73% of youth who are eligible are restrained from running for political offices; thereby affecting the number of youth holding political appointments. In Nigeria, the not too young to run bill' was institute to provide inclusion for youths in the political governance of

the nation. But the bill is yet to gain popular recognition and implementation (Bariledum, 2013).

Enhancing opportunities for young people to participate in politics has become a growing global priority, with organizations like the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) and the United Nations (UN) seeking to collect data and develop strategies to elect a larger share of young people to national parliaments. One recommendation puts forward by the IPU (2016) is to align the ages at which citizens may vote in elections and run for political office. In order to respond to the needs of young people, and to guarantee that their basic human rights are recognized and enforced, young people's active and meaningful participation in their societies and in democratic practices and processes is of crucial importance Meaningful youth participation and leadership require that young people and young people-led organizations have opportunities, capacities, and benefit from an enabling environment and relevant evidence- based programmes and policies at all levels (Kifordu, 2011).

Realizing young people's right to participate and be included in democratic processes and practices is also vital to ensure the achievement of internationally agreed development goals and to refresh the development agenda. Today the global campaign Not Too Young to Run was launched at the first United Nations Forum on Human Rights, Democracy and the Rule of Law taking place at

United Nations Geneva (Adisa, 2008). The campaign, launched by a partnership consisting of the Office of the UN Secretary General's Envoy on Youth, the UN Development Programme (UNDP), the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU), the European Youth Forum (EYF) and the Youth Initiative for Advocacy Growth & Advancement (YIAGA), aims to elevate the promotion of young people's right to run for public office and address the wide-spread issue of age discrimination (Ibrahim, 2019).

Youth constitute a fifth of the World's population. Meanwhile, their participation in the political discourses is very limited. Globally, the average age of parliamentarians is 53 (Anderson, 2017). The minimum age for competing to the parliamentary candidacy is 25 years. This puts into question the inclusion of young peoples in the political spheres and processes. The youth have been recognized for their creative skills and innovative ideas. A critical look at the major political changes and dynamism shows that youth are at the center of the fulcrum. They mostly serve as catalysts for the changes of undemocratic governments and their political systems. The 2011/2012 Arab uprising is case in point. However, due to unfavorable legal architectures, low economic conditions and different discriminatory practices, their contributions and roles in the political arenas were extremely limited. As a result, their involvement in the political process is informal and not yet well recorded. Given the fact that Africa is young in democracy and its political institutions are not well established, youth are excluded from important decision making processes (Oyvaibaire, 2017). Most often than not, governments and policy makers in Africa are reluctant to include youth in the formal political systems. Nowadays, however; a marginal improvement has been shown in Africa, partly because of the rising consciousness of states and the external pressures including globalization and democratizations, which give due emphasis for the youth participation in the political and economic spheres of influences (Maine, 2018).

As a result of lack of political participation of youth within the continent, they are disorganized, unemployed, and vulnerable to radical ideas such that leading demonstrations against government decisions. This has been seen in Sierra Leone, where the disillusioned and unemployed youth had played a great role in establishing the Revolutionary United Front (RUF) and in Rwanda where the youth were at the center in the genocidal. In line with this logic, a movement of young people in Nigeria launched a campaign in 2016 to reduce the age limit to stand as political candidates conceived by YIAGA Africa, a youth-based civil society Organization seeking to promote good governance and youth political

participation, the campaign soon encompassed more than 100 youth organizations and became known by its hashtag 'Not Too Young To Run law' (Faber, 2015).

The Not Too Young To Run law in Nigeria aimed to amend sections 65, 106, 131 and 177 of the Nigerian constitution to reduce the eligibility age for the Houses of Assembly and House of Representatives from 30 to 25 years old, the Senate and Governorship from 35 to 30 years old, and the office of the President from 40 to 35 years old. Sponsored by allies in the House of Representatives and the Senate, the law passed both houses of parliament in July 2017. The proposed amendment was then presented to the 36 Houses of Assembly of the Nigerian states, 33 of which approved the law.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The concept of youth involvement in politics and governance has consistently gain attention in view of the role of youth in the development of the society. Many youths have been found to be involved in politically processes but not elected into public offices. This has greatly affected the participation of youths in the political process. Participation is considered as essential but, the changing political, cultural and economic realities have greatly affected the active participation of youths in politics and governance (Cheng, 2014). Many youths are disengaging from democratic and civic activities and concentrating more on professional careers. According to reports 73% of youth who are eligible are restrained from running for political offices thereby affecting the number of youth holding political appointments. The institution of the bill of 'not too young to run law' has not been widely recognized and implemented. Hence, the need to popularizes the bill. This law provides the age for the House of Representatives to be from 30 years to 25 years and 35 years to 40 years for Senate. However, that of the president to be 40 years. Therefore, the problem confronting the study is to determine the challenges of youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of the "the not too young to run law".

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are to appraise the challenges of youth participation in politics and governance; the assessment of "the not Too young to run law".

The specific objectives of the study include;

1. To investigate the relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society.
2. To find out the challenge of youth participation in politics and governance.

3. To identify the nature and significance of "the not Too young to run law".

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society?
2. Are you aware of the Not Too Young to Run law?
3. Do you think the Not too young to run law is a challenge on Nigeria's youth political participation in 2023 general election?
4. Do you think the signing of Not too young to run law increase the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is NO significant relationship in relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society

H₁: There is a significant relationship in relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society.

H₀: There is NO significant relationship in awareness of the Not Too Young to Run law

H₁: There is a significant relationship in awareness of the Not Too Young to Run law.

H₀: Signing of Not too young to run law is a challenges on Nigeria's youth political participation in 2023 general election

H₁: Signing of Not too young to run law is not a challenges on Nigeria's youth political participation in 2023 general election.

H₀: Signing of Not too young to run law increased the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics.

H₁: Signing of Not too young to run law did not increase the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study shall provide relevant information on the nature and significance of the "the not Too young to run law". It shall also proffer an appraisal of the relevance and challenges of youth participation in politics and governance in the society.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on the appraisal of challenges of youth participation in politics and governance with the assessment of "the not too young to run law".

1.8 Limitation of the Study

The study was confronted with financial and geographical constraints.

1.9 Definition of Terms

Political System Defined: A framework which focus on defining acceptable political methods within the state or nation.

Election Defined: A competition between different political parties for electives public office.

Political Party Defined: This is a political organization which aims to seek and control political power in government.

Youth Defined: This consist of persons within the age of 15-35 years.

Political Participation: This involves any activities that shapes, affect, or involves the political sphere, ranging from voting, attending rally, etc.

Not Too Young To Run: This entail a campaign which seek to reduce the age limit for running elective office in Nigeria and globally.

Bill: A draft of a proposed law presented to the parliament for discussion.

1.10 Organization of the Study

This research work will be segmented into five (5) chapters. Chapter one is the introduction, which contains the background of the study, statement of the result of the problem, research hypotheses, significance of the study, scope and limitation of the study, definitions of terms and organization of the study. Chapter Two relevant to the study and the theoretic posits the literature review and theoretical framework. It explains an introductive view of the subject matter. It Juxtapose the diverse definition of the various concepts such as: democratization, political participation and Not too young to Rule, in relations to the limited views of some known foreign political analyst and scholars. The chapter also examine the theoretical framework viable for the subject matter. Chapter three looks at the historical overview of youth participation in Nigeria politics, Background to youth participation in Nigeria politics since 1960, emerging issues of youth participation in Nigeria politics, favorable strategies put in place by government to enhance youth participation in politics and lastly research methodology. Chapter four will attempt to present data and analyze it. This is an in-depth analysis of the impact of not too Young to Rule Law on Nigeria's youth participation in politics in 2023 general election. Chapter five will attempt to do summary, conclusion and recommendation to the major findings of the research.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter gives an insight into various studies conducted by outstanding researchers, as well as explains terminologies with regards to the problem of political participation in Nigeria. The chapter also gives a resume of the history and present status of the problem delineated by a concise review of previous studies into closely related problems.

2.1 Conceptual Review

Review of literature in research is sine qua non in determining the nature of the research as it provides the basis for the understanding of what others have said or written about the subject matter, several efforts have been made in the past and present to study political participation. It therefore, becomes imperative to review what other scholars have written about democracy and political participation in Nigeria, in order to solve problems associated with it (Bruter, 2009). There are numerous problems associated with lack of proper democratic practices and political participation in Nigeria which includes, gender imbalance, political apathy and total annihilation of the masses by the few aged political elites as argued by many scholars. So, this chapter will take cognizance of those literatures by many scholars on political participation in Nigeria (Putbam, 2011).

2.1.1 Concept of Democracy

Democracy, either as a concept or a system of rule, has become excessively ambiguous in contemporary political analysis. Indeed, there is probably no concept that has been so subjected to varying definitions, antagonistic interpretations and contradictory practices as the concept of democracy, this is not surprising given the fact that democracy has become more and more widely praised and embraced thereby making it more and more difficult to pin down (Pettersson *et al.*, 2014). Politicians from the extreme left to the extreme right always insist that the form of politics or rule they support is the one that is democratic in character (Adebayo, 2009). Democracy can be defined as a system of government in which all qualified adult citizens share supreme power directly or indirectly or through their elected representatives. Abraham Lincoln, whose definition of democracy has become axiomatic, defined it as “the government of the people, by the people and for the people”. The term democracy has been in another occasion been describe as government by consent of the governed.

According to oyovbaire (2017) democracy is a system which seeks to realize a generally recognized common good through a collective initiation and discussion of policy questions concerning public affairs and which delegated authority to agents to implement the broad decisions made by the people

through majority vote. In the often eulogized Greek City States, which Giuseppe Di Palma referred to as the ‘birthplace of democracy’, every inhabitant supposedly had a direct say on issues which directly affected the state. It must be pointed out however that in practice,

Greek democracy was an exclusive one because a large part of the adult population was denied full citizenship i.e. the right to participate in politics whether by attending the meetings of the Sovereign Assembly or by serving in public offices. Not only were women denied the right of full citizenship, but also long term resident aliens (metics) and slaves. Indeed, the slaves were no more than the property of their owners wholly without legal rights. Thus, only the non-slaves were allowed to vote and by 430 BC, nearly half of the total populations of Athens were slaves. Furthermore, Jean Jacque Rousseau (1712-1778), the Enlightenment French social and political theorist and one of the first thinkers to question the basis of the undemocratic and absolute power wielded by Europe’s monarchs, limited his notion of democracy to property owners while John Stuart Mill (1806-1873), the British philosopher-economist, called for the extension of the franchise to the property class only. Moreover, the emergence of modern state meant some loss of individual’s rights and privileges since the state can force its members to carry out certain tasks. Since a state is a legal and political entity with power to require or compel obedience and loyalty from its citizens, in most modern states, while the citizens may be free to express their views, they are made to live under the conditions prescribed by their states (leaders), (Adebayo, 2009).

2.1.1.1 Types of Democracy

Suberu (2019), under mentioned the two major types of Democracy on the following;

- i. **Direct Democracy:** This is a type of democracy where all citizens attend the Assembly and take part in the decision making in order to govern the state or society.
- ii. **Indirect or Representative Democracy:** This is a type of democracy, the citizens through election elect those that will represent and govern the state on their behalf. This type of democracy replaced the direct democracy in modern states as it’s no more possible for everyone to gather in one place in order to take decisions to govern the state as a result of the large size and population of the modern states.

2.1.1.2 Features of Democracy

Maine (2018) identifies in his work concerned features of Democracy, which includes;

- i. Regular and periodic election.
- ii. Assertion of the principles of the rule of law in the constitution and its observance.
- iii. Majority rule in the country.
- iv. Respect for the right of the minority groups.
- v. Equality before the law.
- vi. Guaranteeing fundamental human rights.
- vii. Existence of party system.
- viii. Effective system of changing government.
- ix. Principles of separation of powers.
- x. Freedom of press.

2.1.2 Political Participation

Political participation derives from the freedom to speak out, assemble and associate; the ability to take part in the conduct of public affairs; and the opportunity to register as a candidate, to campaign, to be elected and to hold office at all levels of government. Under international standards, men and women have an equal right to participate fully in all aspects of the political process. Political participation is a basic concept in political science and scholars define the concept in different ways. It may be defined as the actions of private citizens seeking to influence or support Government and politics. Milbrath and Goel uphold that this is a relatively broad definition since it also includes ceremonial and support activities. (Milbrath and Goel, 2012).

However, there are two ways to understand broadness when defining the concept political participation; In terms of the kinds of tools or actions that are included, In terms of the target of the actions. Seen from the first perspective this definition is broad but since the government is the sole target it can also be viewed as a narrow definition. There are other definitions of the concept political participation which I will discuss below. In the discussion on political participation scholars often try to explain human behavior as it relates to the political system but they also recognize that the political system and the political culture have a significant impact on individual political behavior. Still many scholars believe that at a basic level people follow the same behavioral laws irrespective of the culture they live in (Cheng, 2014).

The classical definition of political participation is the one that refers to: “those voluntary activities by which members of a society share in the selection of rulers and directly or indirectly in the formation of public policy” (McClosky, 2014). However, politics today include more than relationships between citizens and their Government.

These scholars are advocates of what William Riker (2007) called a “liberal” model of democracy, an idea which can be summarized in three statements:

- i. Citizens have meaningful preferences only when it comes to which candidates or parties that should have the political power,
- ii. These preferences are expressed only indirect, through a representative system,
- iii. These preferences are independent of the democratic process as such.

With this kind of definition there are not very many remaining tasks for the empirical research. (Robert, 2011) Thus this is a very narrow definition of the concept of political participation compared to Lam’s definition.

2.1.2.1 Rationale behind Political Participation

Participation as a concept transcends political environment, albeit a political scientist views all aspect of the society as political or having political bearings. Anything that involves decision making implementation is political. Anything that has to do with interest articulation and aggregation is political. Participation therefore, may take place in government, organizational, familial and private settings (Faber, 2015).

Some of the reasons why people participate in political and administrative processes have been advanced by Walker (2010) as follow:

- i. Participation can build public support for activities.
- ii. It can educate the public about an agency’s activities.
- iii. Can also facilitate useful information exchange regarding local conditions.
- iv. Participation enables individuals and groups to influence agency decisions in a representational manner.
- v. For political socialization. This involves the process through which an individual acquires his or her own political orientations.

2.1.2.2 Types of Participation

There are two major types of political participation according to Walker (2010) which are;

- i. Conventional and
- ii. Unconventional participation

Unconventional Participation: An unconventional participation involves an uncommon behavior that challenges or defies government channels or the dominant culture, it usually personally stressful for both participants and their opponents. Primary examples of this type of participation are:

- a. Despite its long history, Americans generally disapprove of unconventional political action, and particularly those acts that interfere with daily living (such as occupying buildings)
- b. Unconventional participation has been successful in influencing government decisions, civil rights movement, the Vietnam War.
- c. People participating in unconventional ways (such as direct political action) tend to share three characteristics. d. Distrust of the political system e. A strong sense of political efficacy f. A highly developed sense of group consciousness g. Americans is more likely to participate in unconventional politics than citizens of other democratic countries.

2.1.3 Not Too Young to Run Campaign

“Not Too Young to Run Campaign” is a movement strengthened to increase the vastness of youth political participation globally. According to the Office of the Secretary-General’s Envoy and Youth (OSGEY) in partnership with the InterParliamentary Union (IPU) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 2007, generation of young people is the largest the world has ever known. Half of the global population is under the age of 25, and young people between the ages of 15 and 25 constitute one-fifth of this total. Yet, young people are starkly underrepresented in government and politics at virtually every level. One key factor contributing to low representation of young people in government and politics is an age of candidacy that is significantly higher than the legal voting age. This form of age discrimination is often met with other significant barriers, including social and cultural barriers and discrimination against young candidates (Bruter and Atarrison, 2009).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Theories are the analyst's tools for explanation of political reality. There are a number of theories that deal with such issues as social, economic, and political dominance, including Youth Participation and Politics. These theories in other words deal with group or elite dominance. Such theories include the Elite theory; Marxian class theory, the iron law of oligarchy, etc. Some of these theories of dominance have already been highlighted in the literature review, showing their respective strengths and weaknesses (Adisa, 2008).

This study adopts the Elite Theory for the purpose of analysis. The elite theory is one of the theories of socio-political dominance that has stood the test of time. It has universal applicability, and is also easy to comprehend. Within the elite philosophy, two major schools are manifest, namely: the single elite

and the plural elite models. Common to both models of elite theory is the notion that society is polarized into the elite and the masses. That while the elite are strong and powerful, the masses are weak and are at the receiving end of elite dominance (Anderson, 2017). The single elite theorists argue that there is single elite in society which exercises influence over the masses. The elite they say is cohesive, its influence concentrated and cumulative, and that the elite, in addition to the making and enforcement of policies uses its power to determine conditions for entry of persons to positions of political influence. The plural elite school on the other hand argues that there exist different elites in society which exercise influence over the masses (Oyvaibaire, 2017).

The theory tries to explain the various relationships of power in the society. It states that a small minority consisting of members of the economic and political elites and policy-planning networks hold the most power, and that this power is independent of a state’s democratic election process. In other words, a particular set of people direct the affairs of the society and their children possibly takes over from them and it continues in that circle (Robert *et al.*, 2011).

Under this theory a political system is seen to be divided into two major groups which are what some scholars refer to as the political entrepreneurs otherwise known as the elites and the citizens or the masses who is popularly referred to as what they call the apolitical clay. The elites in this group are those who possess various ideological interests while the average citizens are more or less not aware or even interested in the public affairs of their society. It is based on the notion of groups that this theory more or less gives higher credits to the elite group holding to the fact that the ordinary citizen is incapacitated in administering the state for a smooth running of democracy (Suberu, 2019). All has to come from the wisdom and directives of elites in the state who in the contemporary era are the political leaders who are perceived to possess special skills and knowledge in the state.

2.2.1 Application of Elite Theory to Not Too Young to Run law and Nigeria’s Youth Participation in Politics

At this juncture, it's very crucial to state the fact that Elite theory is the most preferred theory that best explain political participation and the “not too young to run agitation” in Nigeria, the Nigeria political landscape is controlled by cabals, the ruling elites who use the instrument of governance to enrich themselves as they became so powerful (Varma, 2006). Those who control governance are very few in number; they are educated and well organized. The problem in Nigeria politics is elite circulation. The Elite used Political parties as machinery through

which they get hold to political offices which they have strongly influence with their policies and the demanding cost to obtain ticket of a party. They have also been instrumental in shaping political institutions and in like manner the values and interests of political actors. Based on this, Henry Kifordu submits in his paper on “Nigeria Political Executive Elites (2011), that political institutions may be weakened by special elite interests in the Nigerian polity. Political institutions are subjected to the same state control as the major national economic resources and as well as the political elites, the elites constitute the governing class in any modern society. Though, with varying degree of acceptability due to human, group and organizational flaws, the political-elite determines the political fate of the other elites and indeed, the non-elites which most of the young masses agitating for power belongs to (Putnam, 2011). Their preeminent roles as policy-initiators and decision-makers place them on a pedestal far above the rest of society (Odubajo and Alabi 2014).

2.2.2 Criticism of Elitism

The elite theories which had been first advocated against Marxism have been put to searching questions and found lacking. Some of the points of criticism are:

- i. **Elite cannot control the whole sphere of political activity:** The advocates of elite theories wrongly believe that elite can control the whole sphere of political, social and economic activity. An elite may influence one field but it cannot influence all the fields. For example, Dahl holds that economically well-off section of society cannot find any place in the sphere of education. Dahl has beautifully made a distinction between the ‘economic notables’, ‘social notables’ and political leaders.
- ii. **Wealth and political position cannot be proportionate:** The supporters of the elite theory wrongly hold the belief that the wealthy persons may rise to political power and control the political structure. It is not necessary that the most powerful man of the state may be also wealthiest. Besides that, it is also not certain that the wealthiest person may rise to political power. In communist countries the wealth has no role to play. Even in democratic countries like India, though the wealth has played a notable role in the elections, yet all the wealthy persons have not risen to power. Many big capitalists of India may exercise political influence upon the government directly or indirectly but they have not

- iii. **Elite are more concerned about their personal interest than the interest of the whole community:** Supporters of the elite theory wrongly lead us to believe that the elites look to the interests of the whole community. In fact, they never look to the interest of entire society but confine themselves to their own interests.
- iv. **Decision-making does not lie solely in the hands of the elite:** It is argued by prominent supporters of the elite theory that the decisions in the government are generally taken by the elite. When the government takes decisions, several factors influence it and not only the wishes of the elite.
- v. **Ideas of elite never create values:** The supporters of elite theory believe that the ideas of the elite create value for the society but this is only one-sided picture. On the other hand, the truth is that the elite give ideas in accordance with the values recognized by the masses because the elite can never force their values on society.
- vi. **Elite are not cohesive, conscious and conspiratorial:** The main exponents of the elite theory hold that the elite are linked by ties of common interests and they are cohesive, conscious and conspiratorial but it is not so, Fredrick says that, “It is not the class that rules but the class from which the rulers and in whose interest they exercise power.” He further holds that their power is not cohesive because many rival groups hold power in the society.
- vii. **Elite do not rule with their inherent ability:** It has been held that the elites rule any country because of their inherent abilities but it is not so. The hard ‘fact is that they have to rule the country according to the consent of the masses. Even if a small section of the people is alienated from the political system, then it may resort to protests and demonstrations which may paralyze the elite rule and the theory of the elite (Walker, 2010).

2.3 Challenges of Youth Participation in Politics and Governance in Nigeria

The youths in Nigeria have some impediments/challenges working against their efforts to entrench and sustain genuine democracy in Nigeria at large. These among others, are:

- a. **Illiteracy:** this implies inability to read and write by an individual. It is a state of absolute lack of education. Though mostly refers to lack of formal education, the

concept denotes inability to read and write or to obtain western and/or other form of education e.g. Arabic/Qur'anic education. Education, on the other hand, embodied the entire process through which members of the society acquire necessary norms, values and skills which conform to societal standard or which make them fit to the society. In modern society like contemporary Nigeria, education is systematic and organised; characterised by the existence of organised structures and personnel, as well as, accorded criteria for grading of status or certificates in a school system (Umar, 1993). Against this backdrop, the bulk of Nigerian youths is illiterate. UNDP Human Development Report (1996 and 2004) observed that, "apart from the fact that the chunk of Nigerians is grossly illiterate, the number of youths dropping out of school and graduate lacking skills has been on the increase". This has been a major setback to the ability of the youths to support and sustain genuine democratic processes. A considerable number of them are brainwashed and indoctrinated by the politicians to see their role in the democratic growth as thugs or political gangsters, popularly known as, 'Yanbanga' and 'Yankuge'.

Their illiteracy status is being exploited by desperate politicians at the detriment of the youths and the young state. Worse still, the senseless and reckless educational policies, at all levels of governments, have prevented most youths, access to meaningful and sound education.

- b. **Unemployment and Poverty:** unemployment indicates the situation where an individual or group of individuals is/are unable to be gainfully employed as a means of daily survival. It is a state of joblessness where some societal members lack sources of income which is necessary for their social, economic and political integration into the society (Adelekun, 2008, cited in Umar, 2009). Lack of employment, which in most cases is attributed to lack of education, normally breeds poverty amongst the youths. UNDP (2001) avers that, "the number of youths who are out of work and out of school either as graduates or drop-out are increasingly worrisome." Perhaps, there is link between unemployment and poverty and the roles youths are playing in the democratisation process in Nigerian. This means that joblessness and poverty pose a serious threat to the survival of the youths

and their ability to play their expected roles in sustaining the nascent democracy in the state. Invariably, this has compelled them to engage in any dirty and unhealthy kind of work, the common of which is political gangster. Banga and Kuge has remained the most common and gainful jobs for illiterate and semi-illiterate youths in the State since the advent of this democratic dispensation in 1999. Youngsters are in the payroll of all local government councils and development area councils as compensation for the role (i.e. thuggery) they played during 2002 local government election and 2003 general election, and the role they were expected to play in the subsequent election after 2003. In most cases the politicians supply these youths with arms to carry out this devilish role effectively. Unfortunately, however, genuine socio-economic and poverty alleviation policies that will Challenges of Youth Participation in Sustaining Democracy in Nigeria open-up employment opportunities are not pursued or given due attention by the Nigerian Government just in order to maintain the status quo; hence making the youths susceptible to the dangerous idea of political thuggery.

- c. **Lack of Formidable and Genuine Youth Organisation and Leadership:** most youths do not form a vibrant youth organisation that can pursue youth development policies and support the bid to substantive and sustainable democracy in Nigeria and Nigeria, to be specific. Where there are so called youth organisations, they are spear headed by elders in the disguise of youth. Thus, this can be proven by the fact that most of the heads of youth organisations are persons aged above 40 or sometimes even 60 plus (Raman, 2007). This situation has been affecting the roles of youths in supporting and sustaining democracy in Nigeria. The present president of Nigeria Youth Council and his predecessor, Haliru Wakaso and Umar U. Shehu, respectively; present youth leader of Nigeria Peoples Democratic Party (P.D.P.), Alhaji Abdullahi Baba Sale to mention but a few, are all example of youth leaders above 40 years of age. Thus, they may not necessarily give youth development programmes much priority or effectively pioneer the crusade for youth positive participation and contribution in Nigerian democratisation process.

METHODOLOGY

3.0 The focus of this study is on the challenges of Youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of 'The Not Too Young to run Law'. In this chapter, the various procedures used in collecting data shall be discussed. This chapter is made up of research design, population of study, sample and sampling techniques, instrument of data collection, validity of instrument, method of data collection and data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The research design adopted for this study is the qualitative and quantitative research design, aimed at examining the challenges of Youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of 'The Not Too Young to run Law'.

The cross-sectional research is a research approach in which the researchers investigate the state of affairs in a population at a certain point in time (Akoka, 2013). The study design is characterized by its ability to take place at a single point in time, it does not involve manipulating variables, it allows researchers to look at numerous variables at once and it is oftentimes used to look at the prevailing characteristics in a given population. In cross sectional research design, data is gathered through interviews, questionnaires and focus groups over a certain period of time which may be in the past or the present and then analyze the results. According to Kari Pearson, it involves a measure of reliability by comparing observed frequency distributions (O) with theoretical or expected distribution (E0).

3.2 Population of the Study

Most educational phenomena consist of a large number of units and it would be impracticable, if not impossible to test, to interview or observe each unit of the population under controlled conditions in order to arrive at principles having universal validity. Some population are so large that their study would be expensive in terms of time, efforts and manpower (Asika 2006). (Asika 2006) viewed population as any collection of specific group of human beings or non-human entities such as objects, educational institutions, time units, geographical areas, prices of wheat or salaries draw by individuals. Eboh (2009), further posited that the survey researcher is interested in some characteristics of the population or universe but he uses a carefully selected sample from the population for intensive study of the characteristics of the population. The population in Nigeria is currently 200 million populations according to world population review of which the youth dominate 65% of the population. Therefore, the population of the study is 65% of 200 million which is 130,000,000.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample technique for this study is purposive sampling technique. The choice of this technique is informed by the nature of the topic under review. The technique was considered appropriate because, it enable the researcher to select respondents who have adequate knowledge and who can provide relevant information on "The challenges of Youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of the Not Too Young to run law in 2023 General Elections".

Consequently, the sample size of this study is derived using the Taro Yamane

formula The Yamane formula is thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

N = population size and

e = is the marginal error, (i.e. e = 0.05)

Since the population of this study is 130,000,000 (One Hundred and Thirty million) the sample size was derived through the following equation,

$$N = 130,000,000 / (1 + 130,000,000)(0.05)^2$$

$$n = 12,549 / (1 + 130,000,000)(0.0025)$$

$$n = 12,549 / 1 + 130,000,000 * 0.0025$$

$$n = 12,549 / 1 + 325000$$

$$n = 12,549 / 325001$$

$$n = 399.99$$

From the foregoing, the sample size for this study is 400.

3.4 Method of Data Collection

Methods refer to that range of approaches used in research to gather data which are to be used as a basis for inference and interpretation, for explanation and prediction (Eboh, 2009). In order to ensure high degree of empiricism and factualism in the validity of and findings of the study, a blend of both primary source and secondary source of data collection were adopted.

3.4.1 Primary Data

The study was relying on both quantitative and qualitative data to be sourced by a combination of open-ended and closed ended questionnaire. Primary data are those which are collected afresh and for the first time and thus happen to be original in character. There are several methods of collecting primary data, particularly in survey research. They include: (i) observation method, (ii) interview

method, (iii) through questionnaires, (iv) through schedules and (v) other methods which include (a) warrant cards; (b) distributor audits; (c) pantry audits; (d) consumer panels ;(e) using mechanical devices ;(f) through projective techniques; (g) depth interviews and (h) content analysis (Asika, 2006). The degree of reliability of primary sources is considered high in social science because of its unprocessed or raw nature (Olorunfemi, 2004). Also the primary source is seen as reliable because the data from primary source are direct information from the participants or key witnesses. The possibility of distortion or exaggeration is however, not unlikely. Quantitative data indicates what people have said in their own words about their experiences and interactions in natural settings, and after their careful analysis and depth answers to the research questions of decision makers and information users. (Asika, 2006) emphasized that; quantitative data provides depth and detail. Depth and detail emerge through quotation and careful description.

A. Questionnaire Administration

A questionnaire is a device consisting of series of questions dealing with some psychological, social, educational, etc topics sent or given to an individual or a group of individuals, with the object of obtaining data with regards to some problems under investigation. Eboh (2009) state that in general the word questionnaire refers to a device for securing answers to series of questions by using a form which the respondents fill himself. Thomas (2006), sees questionnaire as a systematic compilation of questions that are administered to a sample of population from which information is desired.

To collect data for the study, a set of 400 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents on "The challenges of Youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of the Not Too Young to run law in 2023 General Elections" Out of the 400 questionnaires, 150 were administered to Political party members and aspirants, 150 to Nigeria youths and 100 to staff of YIAGA and Political analyst.

B. Conduct of Interview

The interviews were restricted to limited people that have knowledge on the "The challenges of Youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of the Not Too Young to run law" The YIAGA initiative platform in Nigeria are targeted. The researcher envisages that there may be some elements of opportunistic sampling in that chance meeting may occur with informed experts thereby presenting opportunity for further interviews. For the purpose of effective planning, 5 key informants who fall within the parameters of interest have been identified for Key Informant Interview (KII) (Kindly see Appendix II for the interview format). These

number is manageable and the researcher could easily revisit them where the need to arises. These key informants (KI) are people with requisite knowledge, theoretical and field experiences that spans several years in the area of "The impact of not too young to rule law on Nigeria's youth participation in 2023 general elections. Hence they have been carefully selected to offer wide ranging views.

3.4.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data means data that are already available i.e they refer to data which have already been collected and analyzed by someone else. Secondary data may either be published or unpublished data. Usually published data are available in: (a) various publications of the central, states and local governments; (b). various publications of foreign government or international bodies and their subsidiary organizations; (c). technical trade journals; (d). books, magazines and newspapers; (e). reports and publications of various associations connected with business and industry, banks, stock exchange, etc;(f). report prepared by research scholars, universities etc. in different fields; and (g). public records and statistics, historical documents, and other sources of published information (Eboh 2009). The sources of unpublished data are many; they may be found in diaries, letters, unpublished biographies and autobiographies and also may be available with scholars and research workers, trade associations, labour bureaus and other public/private individuals and organizations. Other sources of information like the Internet will be explored. Most of the materials were sourced from the University of Abuja library and National Library Abuja.

3.5 Tools and Methods of Data Analysis

Data analysis involves a number of closely related operations which are performed with the purpose of summarizing the collected data and organizing these in such a manner that they answer the research questions. In a research of this kind that examines "The challenges of Youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of the Not Too Young to run law" Data Analysis and Interpretation is very essential. Data collected shall be presented, interpreted and analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative techniques.

A. Quantitative Tool:

These are tools that are employed in quantitative research and they include; Frequency Distribution and Simple Percentages, T-test (dependent and independent variables), Chi-square, Regression Analysis, Pearson Correlation Co-efficient and Analysis of Variance. Quantitative method of research is helpful to bring about some measures of objectivity. The statistical and mathematical

methods as tools for analysis are free from subjective bias Ozohu-Suleiman (2005) the chief job of data analysis in field studies consist basically of summarizing the field notes by means of taxonomies or flowcharts. Data presentation, analysis and interpretation of this work was done through the instrumentality of simple percentage and chi-square.

B. Qualitative Tool:

Content analysis was used to analyze data realized from the field exercise on “The challenges of Youth participation in politics and governance, the assessment of the Not Too Young to run law”. The challenges of not too young to rule law on Nigeria's youth participation in 2023 general elections”. Content analysis is a systematic analysis and description of the content of communication media. Content analysis is a research technique for the objective, systematic and quantitative description of the manifest content of communication. It enables one to know the attitude of the mass communication system towards a country, a system or an issue, whether internal or international.

It is a specialized way of coding techniques. According to Asika (2006), content analysis aims at converting recorded raw phenomena into data can be treated essentially in a scientific manner so that a system of knowledge may be built up. Books, Journals, newspapers and the likes will be analyzed.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

This chapter is concerned with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data collected. As reflected in chapter three, a total of 400 questionnaires were distributed out of which 300 were retrieved and duly filled by the respondents, this amount is 90% of the total questionnaires. For the purpose of easy understanding, simple percentages and frequencies scores were used to analyse the data. The chapter is divided into two sections. The first section deals with the descriptive analysis of the bio-data of respondents. The second section dwells on the evaluation of propositions.

4.1.1 Section A: Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Personal Data.

Table 4.1: Sex

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female	140	46.7%
Male	160	53.3%
Total	300	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Fig 4.1: Chart representing the Sex of the Respondents

Source: Field survey, 2023.

In the table and chart above, the respondents are classified according to their gender, 140 respondents representing 46.7% are females, 160 respondents representing 53.3% are males. This implies that majority of the respondents are males.

Table 4.2: Age

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-25 years	240	80.00%
26-35 years	40	13.3%
Above 35 years	20	6.7%
Total	300	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Fig 4.2: Chart representing the Age of the Respondents.

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

In the table and chart above the respondents are classified according to their Age bracket, 240 respondents representing 80% fall in between 18 – 25 yrs, 40 respondents representing 13.3% fall in between 26 – 35 yrs, 20 respondents representing 6.7% fall between 36 years and above. This implies that majority of the respondents fall between 18 – 25yrs of age.

Table 4.3: Marital Status

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	255	85%
Divorced	10	3.3%
Married	30	10%
Separated	5	1.7%
Total	300	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Fig 4.3: The Marital Status of the Respondent

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

In the table and chart above the respondents are classified according to their marital status, 255 respondents representing 85% are Single, 10 respondents representing 3.3% are Divorced, 30 respondents representing 10% are married, 5 respondents representing 1.7% are widowed. This implies that majority of the respondents are single.

Section B: Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Opinion.

Question 1: What is the relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society?

Table 4.4: Showing the Frequency of the relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society.

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	250	83.3%
No	50	16.7%
Total	300	100.0%

Source: Research Questionnaire, 2023.

The table above shows the participation in politics, frequency and percentage of respondents on the relevant of youth participation in the society. 250 respondents with 83.3% participated in politics, why 50 respondents with 16.7% did not participate in politics in the society.

Question 2: Are you aware of the Not Too Young to Run law?

Table 4.5: Showing the frequency of awareness of Not Too Young to Run law.

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	270	90%
No	30	10%
Total	300	100.0%

Source: Research Questionnaire, 2023.

The table above shows the opinions of respondents on the awareness of Not Too young to run law. 270 respondents which represents 90% are aware of the Not too young to run law while 30 respondents represent 10% are not aware of the Not too young to Run law. This implies that majority of the respondents are aware of the Not too young to run law.

Question 3: Do you think the Not too young to run law is a challenge on Nigeria's youth political participation in 2023 general election?

Table 4.19: Showing the frequency of Question 3

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	180	60%
No	120	40%
Total	300	100.0%

Source: Research Questionnaire, 2023.

From the table above, it shows that 180 respondents representing 60% agreed that not too young to run law is a challenge on Nigeria's youth political participation in 2023 general election while 120 respondents representing 40% disagree. This implies that the majority of the respondents agreed.

Question 4: Do you think the signing of Not too young to run law increase the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics?

Table 4.34: Showing the frequency of Question

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	242	80.7%
No	58	19.3%
Total	300	100.0%

Source: Research Questionnaire, 2023.

From the table above, it shows that 242 respondents representing 80.7% agreed that the signing of not too young to run law increased the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics while 58 respondents representing 19.3% disagree. This implies that the majority of the respondents agreed.

4.2 Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: There is NO significant relationship in relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society

H₁: There is a significant relationship in relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society.

Step 1:

Variable	Yes	No	Total
Male	150 (40%)	20 (6.7%)	170
Female	120 (40%)	10 (3.3%)	130
Total	270	30	300

Step 2: calculate the Expected Value

$$X_2 = \frac{CT \times RT}{GT}$$

Where:

CT= Column total

RT = Row total

GT = Grand total

$$E_1 = \frac{270 \times 170}{300} = \frac{45900}{300} = 153$$

$$E_2 = \frac{270 \times 130}{300} = \frac{35100}{300} = 117$$

$$E_3 = \frac{30 \times 170}{300} = \frac{5100}{300} = 17$$

$$E_4 = \frac{30 \times 130}{300} = \frac{3900}{300} = 13$$

Step 3: Apply chi-square methodology

$$X_2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$$

O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$X_2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$
15	15	-3	9	0.06
0	3			
12	11	3	9	0.08
0	7			
20	17	3	9	0.53
10	30	-3	9	0.69

$$\Sigma = 1.36$$

$$X_{2cal} = 1.36$$

$$X_{2tab} = df$$

$$DF = (c-1) (r-1)$$

$$= (2-1) (2-1) = (1) (1)$$

$$= 1 \times 1 = 1$$

Significant difference = 0.5

Therefore, X_{2tab} = 1 under 0.5 in four figure table

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84$$

Step 4: Test of Decision rule

$$X_{2cal} = 1.36$$

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84.$$

Therefore, since the calculated value at 0.5 level of significant is less than table value, we accept H₀ and reject H₁.

Based on the calculation above, there is NO significant relationship in relevance of youth participation in politics and governance in the society.

Hypothesis 2

H₀: There is NO significant relationship in awareness of the Not Too Young to Run law

H₁: There is a significant relationship in awareness of the Not Too Young to Run law.

Step 1

Variable	Yes	No	Total
Male	160 (53.3%)	0(0%)	160
Female	140 (46.7%)	0 (0%)	140
Total	300	0	300

Step 2: calculate the Expected Value

$$X_2 = \frac{CT \times RT}{GT}$$

Where:

CT= Column total

RT = Row total

GT = Grand total

$$E_1 = \frac{300 \times 160}{300} = \frac{4800}{300} = 160$$

$$E_2 = \frac{300 \times 140}{300} = \frac{4200}{300} = 140$$

$$E_3 = \frac{0 \times 160}{300} = \frac{0}{300} = 0$$

$$E_4 = \frac{0 \times 140}{300} = \frac{0}{300} = 0$$

Step 3: Apply chi-square methodology

$$X^2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$$

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	$X^2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$
160	160	0	0	0.00
140	140	0	0	0.00
0	0	0	0	0.00
0	0	0	0	0.00
$\Sigma = 0.00$				

$$X_{2cal} = 1.36$$

$$X_{2tab} = df$$

$$DF = (c-1)(r-1) = (2-1)(2-1)$$

$$= (1)(1)$$

$$= 1 \times 1 = 1$$

Significant difference = 0.5

Therefore, $X_{2tab} = 1$ under 0.5 in four figure table

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84$$

Step 4: Test of Decision rule

$$X_{2cal} = 0.00$$

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84.$$

Therefore, since the calculated value at 0.5 level of significant is less than table value, we accept H_0 and reject H_1 .

Hypothesis 3

H_0 : Signing of Not too young to run law is a challenges on Nigeria's youth political participation in 2023 general election.

H_1 : Signing of Not too young to run law is not a challenges on Nigeria's youth political participation in 2023 general election.

Variable	Yes	No	Total
Male	80 (26.7%)	100 (33.3%)	180
Female	47(15.7%)	28(24.3%)	120
Total	127	173	300

Step 2: calculate the Expected Value

$$X^2 = \frac{CT \times RT}{GT}$$

Where:

CT= Column total

RT = Row total

GT = Grand total

$$E_1 = \frac{127 \times 180}{300} = \frac{22860}{300} = 76.2$$

$$E_2 = \frac{127 \times 120}{300} = \frac{15240}{300} = 50.8$$

$$E_3 = \frac{173 \times 180}{300} = \frac{31140}{300} = 103.8$$

$$E_4 = \frac{173 \times 120}{300} = \frac{20760}{300} = 69.2$$

Step 3: Apply chi-square methodology

$$X^2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$$

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	$X^2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$
80	76.2	3.8	14.44	0.19
47	50.8	-3.8	14.44	0.28
100	103.8	-3.8	14.44	0.14
73	69.2	3.8	14.44	0.21
$\Sigma = 0.82$				

$$X_{2cal} = 1.36$$

$$X_{2tab} = df$$

$$DF = (c-1)(r-1)$$

$$= (2-1)(2-1)$$

$$= (1)(1)$$

$$= 1 \times 1 = 1$$

Significant difference = 0.5

Therefore, $X_{2tab} = 1$ under 0.5 in four figure table

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84$$

Step 4: Test of Decision rule

$$X_{2cal} = 0.82$$

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84.$$

Therefore, since the calculated value at 0.5 level of significant is less than table value, we accept H_0 and reject H_1 .

Based on the calculation above, The Not Too Young to Run law is a challenges on Nigeria’s youth political participation in 2023 general election

Hypothesis 4

H_0 : Signing of Not too young to run law increased the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics.

H_1 : Signing of Not too young to run law did not increase the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics.

Variable	Yes	No	Total
Male	130 (43.3%)	30(10%)	160
Female	112 (37.3%)	28(9.3%)	140
Total	242	58	300

Step 2: calculate the Expected Value

$$X_2 = \frac{CT \times RT}{GT}$$

Where:

CT= Column total

RT = Row total

GT = Grand total

$$E_1 = \frac{242 \times 160}{300} = \frac{38720}{300} = 129.07$$

$$E_2 = \frac{242 \times 140}{300} = \frac{33880}{300} = 112.93$$

$$E_3 = \frac{58 \times 160}{300} = \frac{9280}{300} = 30.93$$

$$E_4 = \frac{58 \times 140}{300} = \frac{8120}{300} = 27.07$$

Step 3: Apply chi-square methodology

$$X_2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$$

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	$X_2 = \frac{(E - O)^2}{E}$
130	129.07	0.93	0.865	0.008
112	112.93	-0.93	0.865	0.008
30	30.73	-0.93	0.865	0.28
28	27.07	0.93	0.865	0.032
				$\Sigma = 0.076$

$$X_{2cal} = 1.36$$

$$X_{2tab} = df$$

$$DF = (c-1) (r-1)$$

$$= (2-1) (2-1)$$

$$= (1) (1)$$

$$= 1 \times 1 = 1$$

$$\text{Significant difference} = 0.5$$

Therefore, $X_{2tab} = 1$ under 0.5 in four figure table

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84$$

Step 4: Test of Decision rule

$$X_{2cal} = 0.076$$

$$X_{2tab} = 3.84.$$

Therefore, since the calculated value at 0.5 level of significant is less than table value, we accept H_0 and reject H_1 .

Based on the calculation above, the signing of Not too young to run law increased the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics.

4.3 Discussion of findings

The findings of this study revealed some interesting facts based on the data gathered from the questionnaire. We shall proceed to discuss the study’s findings in line with the objective of the study and more specifically the research questions.

- a. What is the reason behind the formulation of Not too young to rule law?

Majority (73.3%) of the respondents admitted that the youths are marginalized in Nigeria politics. Majority (90%) also agreed that Youth inclusiveness will lead to an ideal democracy in Nigeria political system. Majority (92.3%) also agreed that Government can increase the youth morale by inculcating them into governance and administration. Youths inclusion into politics will bring about equality (80.7%) and there must be changes in electoral act to increase Nigeria’s youth political participation.

- b. What is the impact of Not too young to rule law on Nigerian youth participation in politics?

Almost all the respondents (90%) were aware of the Not too young to run law, only 10% of the respondents are not aware of the Not too young to run law. 60% of the respondents agreed that the Not Too Young to Run Law is a positive impact on Nigeria's youth participation in 2023 general election. 80.7% of the respondent admit that the signing of Not too young to run law increase the percentage and awareness of youth participation in Nigeria politics.

- c. What are the challenges confronting youth participation in Nigerian politics?

The challenges confronting youth participation in Nigeria politics ranges from, not being a member of political party, lack of voter's card, god-fatherism, money politics, lack of funds, weak political socialization, inexperience, inferiority complex, government decision/policies and lastly choice of candidacy.

- d. What is the level of youth marginalization in political participation in Nigeria?

The percentage of youths in House of assembly before the signing of not too young to run was 6% which increased to 12.2% after the signing of not too young to run. The percentage of youths in House of representatives as at 2015 was 0.8% which latter increased to 11.7% in 2023. The youths are therefore highly marginalized in Nigeria politics compare to other countries.

5.1 Summary of Findings

This research is both qualitative and quantitative study, it focusses more on the challenges of youth participation in politics and governance; the assessment of "the not too young to run law". Over the years, the percentage of youth participation in general election has been a bone of contention, this marginalization lead to Not too young to run campaign movement in 2022 prior to the 2023 election, there has been no chances for youth aspirants in Nigeria politics. The Not too young to run law was signed into law in 2018 of which reduced the age of youth aspirants into electable offices. The findings of this research discover, that most individuals are aware about the Not too young to run campaign bill and the dynamism in Nigeria politics, which is as result of the marginalization of youths who happen to be the highest percentage of Nigeria's population but are still marginalized in Nigeria politics by the minority or the incumbent political leaders. This shows that the Not too young to run law and campaign came at the right time and it shows the readiness of the youth to take over government.

This research also shows that, the youths are not partisan in politics, which as well as lead to the increase of their marginalization in Nigeria politics. High percentage of the youths had access to voter's cards, but failed to participate due to loss of hope, election sequencing among others. These as also reduced the chances of youths to take over the Nigeria politics. The Not too young to run law also increased the percentage of youth aspirants in 2023 general election of which many lost at the primarily level due to the party politics played and this has also reduced the percentage of youth aspirants in office after the election.

The research work also finds out that the problems of youth participation in politics even after the signing of not too young to run includes: god-fatherism, lack of funds, inexperience, inferiority complex, non-partisan, election sequencing, choice of party, monetization of Nigeria politics among others. These problems have reduced the impact of the signing of Not too young to run law.

This research also finds out, that to solve the issue of political participation and youth inclusiveness in Nigeria politics, the family, religious group, political party and government will serve as the best tool and instrument to attain equality and an ideal democracy. The issues are to be solved from the background of political socialization, which is the family, religious groups, political party, mass media, government of which will reduce the marginalization of the youths in politics, solve inferiority complex, and will give a sense of belonging. The research also discovered that the electoral act must also outline a certain percentage of youth aspirant which every political parties must take cognisance of in any election. This will as well serve as a tool to include youth into politics. Likewise, the appointment of youths into offices can also serve as a tool to include youths into politics. The signing of the not too young to run bill, to a great extent has a great impact on youth participation in 2023 general election and as well increase the level of awareness of youth in Nigeria politics compared to the previous elections. The signing of the bill increased the percentage of youths from 6.8% in 2015 to 18.5% in 2023 in both House of Assembly and National Assembly.

There are so many challenges after the signing of the bill raring from god-fatherism, cost of nomination form, inexperience, party politics, low voters turnout among others. These factors were being faced by youth aspirants in the 2023 election.

5.2. Conclusion

The youth dividend in Nigeria is significant. Unfortunately, the attention given to it is considerably limited. This study attest that if the young population in Nigeria is utilized properly, it would be a potential resource to uplift the continent

and to see the Nigeria everybody wants and as well an ideal democracy. Unless and otherwise, as it was experienced during the 2011/12 Arab uprising and popular demonstration, the youth of Africa would become a threat for any governments that exclude the issues of youth participation in her political system. So, youth inclusion in the political aspects of Nigeria is very critical in a sense that it is a great machinery to reinvent the governance structure of Nigeria. Therefore, creating an enabling and equitable environment for youth in Nigeria politics is unquestionable.

5.3 Recommendation

As the findings of the study revealed that the youth in Nigeria are largely excluded from the political discourse of the country. Thus, to bring youth into the political florals of Nigeria and to utilize their immense potential, the following recommendations are provided. From the global to the national and local levels, the youth-related issues should be the priority areas. Though policy adoptions are important steps towards youth inclusions, their implementations are of paramount importance. Therefore, in every developmental agenda, youth should place in the forefront. In effect, it could be possible to utilize the full capacity of these politically and economically active segments of the population.

Nigeria and individual states have to involve youth in all levels and areas of policy making and developmental plans. For doing so, a national disaggregated data about the youth and their participation is highly required. If Nigeria can do that, it will be able to make informed and evidence-based decisions. One of the findings of the study shows that young Nigerians are largely marginalized from political processes and most of them feel hopelessness about their futures and their inclusion in various decision making processes. They thought that violence could be a viable solution to get what they lost because of irresponsible governments. Therefore, it is an important message for Nigerian governments to be aware of that if they continue as usual, they will confront with the young people who is revolting and restless. The Arab revolt was a good example for this. Therefore, youth participation and representation from local to national and international level is a timely and long lasting solution.

This research work shows that the reason why the not too young to run bill formulated and signed is to include the youths at the decision making of Nigeria politics. Therefore, there should be more trainings, symposium, social media enlighten posts on the reasons why the bill was formulated and as well to increase the awareness of the youth in Nigeria politics. If the youths must be at the for a of Nigeria

politics, they must as well know the problems and as well provide lasting solution to such problem.

The challenges of Not too young to rule law on Nigerian youth participation in politics cannot be over emphasize. The law as increased the awareness of youths to Nigeria politics and as well increased the percentage of youths into elected offices. Also they are different records of how some youths have been appointed into offices by the government. The impact of not too young to run therefore must be known to the public, those who benefited from it should serve as testimonies to others and as well bring about innovative ideas that can develop Nigeria as a whole. The challenges confronting youth participation in Nigerian politics in Nigeria politics includes; god fatherism, monetary politics, inferiority complex and inexperience has been a major stumbling block to Nigeria youths. There should be a policy to reduce and regulate the price of nomination forms and well to include youth aspirant as nominees of any political party. Youths should as well enrol for value leadership concept in as to reduce the inferiority complex and as well give them experience on ways to serve as a leader. The level to which the youths are being marginalized was very high, not until the introduction of not too young to run law. Youth should therefore create opportunities for themselves by creating an awareness of their competency. The youth should create a table to eat which will force the old to dine with them. The youth should not wait for the old to finish eating before taking charge. The emerge youths in offices should make a great use of the opportunity by bringing in innovative ideas that will help develop the society. The summary of recommendation of the study are:

- i. Government should give an enabling environment for the youths to participate in politics by appointing the youths into offices and as well electoral offices.
- ii. The youths should be more organized by forming one political party so as to reach a consensus interests and bring about success in any elective post vied for.
- iii. The youths should enrol for leadership coaching and institutions so as to learn some leadership skills needed.
- iv. The religious institution and family should serve a good agent of socialization to the youths. This will as well change youths mind sets and reduce the level of inferiority complex.
- v. The youths should also enrol for voluntary activities in their society, this will increase their familiarity about the societal problems and ay to solve them.
- vi. The electoral act should mandate certain percentage of youth aspirant from all registered political parties.

- vii. INEC should regulate the cost of Nomination forms within the registered political parties.

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